

Understanding the Implementation of Open Research Training across UK Institutions

Insights from the UK Reproducibility Network Open Research Programme (v2.4)

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Abstract

This qualitative evaluation study explores the barriers and enablers of implementation of open research training at participants' institutions following attendance at a UK Reproducibility Network (UKRN) Train-the-Trainer (T3) course, delivered within the UKRN Open Research Programme (September 2021—August 2026).

It addresses three questions:

- How do T3 participants implement, adapt, and embed open research training within their institutions?
- What institutional conditions act as barriers or enablers of that embedding?
- What individual, social, and structural factors shape whether these practices become normalised in institutional culture and practice?

Small group interviews (n=9 participants across four sessions) were analysed using Normalisation Process Theory (NPT) as a deductive coding framework. The NPT constructs were operationalised to capture how trainers made sense of the programme, engaged with it, enacted it, and evaluated it. Trainers typically described themselves as motivated and capable, and recognised the value of training on Open Research. However, effective participation in the onward delivery expected as part of the Train-the-Trainer programme depended on institutional conditions. To assess impact and quality of the training they delivered, trainers relied on informal cues and on optional post-session surveys. Only infrequently did such informal evidence reach the programme level in a way that could be acted upon. The central finding is that effective onward delivery depends more on local institutional conditions than on the quality of the training itself. We characterise this trainer-level (T3) implementation work; the downstream propagation of training through local delivery, and a cross-stage synthesis, are the subject of a companion study.

Introduction

Open research—encompassing open access publishing, open data/materials, preregistration, reproducible workflows, and related practices across disciplines—has become a policy priority for research funders and institutions internationally (UNESCO 2021; UKRI 2022). The discourse around open research connects these practices with a range of potential benefits, including greater accessibility, transparency, interoperability and reusability of research, improved collaboration dynamics, and wider social benefits. Evidence for these benefits is mixed and context-dependent. It is therefore unsurprising that adoption of open research practices remains uneven, with surveys consistently showing gaps between researchers stated support for open research and their actual behaviour (Christensen et al. 2020; Haven and Van Grootel 2019). Closing this gap requires not only meta-research and policy direction, but also approaches to capacity building that make open research actionable in specific research settings.

As with open research practices themselves, uptake of open research training differs markedly by local context. A Train-the-Trainer model (henceforth T3) makes these dynamics especially visible. In the T3 model, training typically cascades from a centrally-administered programme to local trainers who deliver training to individuals within their institutions (henceforth T1 delivery). The aims may include both changed behaviour, and changes to institutional routines. In principle, this model offers both economies of scale and responsiveness to local needs. Its effectiveness, however, depends on several points of coordination: between central programme design and participants, between trainers and their institutions, and between trainers and their local trainees (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Train-the-trainer model as deployed within the UKRN's Open Research Programme: Training providers, such as the Center for Open Science (COS), delivered train-the-trainer courses; participants in those courses (A, B, C, etc.) delivered local training at their institutions.

Our focus in this paper is on how a national open research training programme interacts with the institutional routines and support structures through which the benefits of train-the-trainer participation could arise.

The UK Reproducibility Network (UKRN) has operated one such programme across 24 institutions as part of its Open Research Programme (ORP). The aim of the ORP is “Growing and Embedding Open Research in Institutional Culture and Practice”, as per the title of the Research England grant that funded the programme. The training intervention was part of a broader conception of that aim, with “Training” comprising one of five constituent work packages in the ORP. A focused inquiry into the training-specific aspects of this programme is useful not only for learning about how and whether open research training works, but also how a distributed change programme succeeds or fails.

The empirical basis for the investigation reported here was small-group interviews with nine Train-the-Trainer participants (n=9); the trainee-facing phase is reserved for a companion study (see *Summary of findings and future work*).

Challenges in embedding open research practice

Emerging research has begun to document the societal and economic impact of open research practices (Tennant et al., 2016; Cole et al. 2024; Tspouri et al. 2025). Yet embedding open research principles into research culture remains challenging at multiple levels: individual researchers may lack knowledge or confidence; institutional incentive and reward structures often do not support open practices; and sustaining newly introduced practices requires ongoing institutional commitment (Nosek et al. 2015; Munafò 2019; Armeni et al. 2021). Practices also differ considerably across disciplines, with open research practice still uncommon in some fields (Hardwicke et al. 2020; Armeni et al. 2021). Surveys consistently show a gap between researchers stated support for open practices and their actual behaviour (Christensen et al. 2020; Nosek et al. 2015). Training is a natural response to many of these considerations, with the view that it can raise methodological awareness among those who do not yet have it, and can help convert existing motivation into practicable, normalised routines, contributing to change in both individual practice and institutional culture.

However, while training satisfaction and growth in knowledge are routinely achievable, behaviour change and organisational impact tend to depend on conditions beyond the training itself. Steinert et al.'s (2006) systematic review of faculty development found that three institutional conditions — formal support, peer networks, and protected time — moderated whether training translated into sustained practice. The training itself is necessary, but not sufficient for sustained behaviour change. Similarly, Greenhalgh et al.'s (2004) review of innovation diffusion in health-service organisations shows that whether a new practice is taken up, or not, depends both on properties of the practice itself (e.g., complexity, fit with existing routines) and on the local context that has to receive it.

Cascade models, such as Train-the-trainer, introduce a layer of indirection: train intermediaries, who then deliver locally. Benefits include both cost-effectiveness and the possibility of local adaptation. However, cascade models are known to attenuate the training as it passes down the chain: fidelity (how closely T3-delivered training resembles what trainers themselves received), confidence (how secure trainers feel delivering material outside their primary expertise), and reach (the size and diversity of audiences that locally delivered training actually attains) all diminish at each cascade step unless the programme actively supports adaptation (Orfaly et al., 2005).

Institutional support interacts with both the feasibility of T3→T1 delivery and local practice change. The implementation science literature distinguishes adoption, implementation, and sustainability (Fixsen et al., 2005). Individual adoption (a trainer delivers a session) can occur without subsequent institutional implementation (the practice is actually embedded in routines) or sustainability (the practice persists beyond the individual). Sen's (1999) capability approach adds a useful way to think about the intermediating conversion factors—such as time, recognition, and institutional backing—that determine whether a formal opportunity becomes a real and durable capability. These literatures converge on a general claim: training alone does not produce sustained practice change.

Methods

The qualitative analysis is based on deductive coding of small-group interview transcripts using Normalisation Process Theory as the framework. The study was preregistered on the Open Science Framework (<https://osf.io/c6srk>).

Reporting standards for small-sample qualitative research have converged over the past decade in ways that bear directly on how a study like this should be presented. Three are now effectively expected. First, sample size is judged not by counting but by *adequacy for the analytic task*: rather than invoking saturation as a numeric stopping rule, recent guidance frames sufficiency in terms of information power. In other words, the more relevant the sample and the sharper the analytic aim, the fewer participants are needed (Malterud et al. 2016). Saturation itself is reframed as the point at which the most salient ideas, not all possible items, have been obtained (Hennink et al. 2017). Second, transparency of analytic procedure — independent multi-coder coding with explicit adjudication of disagreements — has become the recognised guarantor of rigour in team-based deductive analysis (O'Brien et al. 2014). Third, reporting against a named checklist is increasingly treated as a baseline expectation: the Consolidated Criteria for Reporting Qualitative Research (COREQ) for interview and focus-group studies (Tong et al. 2007), complemented by preregistration and accessible data as markers of methodological soundness. We follow these conventions throughout and defend our sample as fit for characterising trainer-side implementation work rather than apologise for its size, report our two-coder-plus-adjudicator procedure in full, preregistered the study on the OSF, and supply a completed COREQ checklist (S3 Table).

Qualitative analysis using Normalisation Process Theory

Normalisation Process Theory (NPT) was suitable as a primary analytic framework because the programme's central theme is how open research becomes embedded in institutional practice and culture. This is a social process question, not an individual behaviour change question. ^[Note 1]

NPT characterises the multi-faceted work through which new practices become operationalised, via four main constructs—Coherence, Cognitive Participation, Collective Action, and Reflexive Monitoring (C. May and Finch 2009; C. May et al. 2015). It has been used extensively in healthcare implementation research (McEvoy et al. 2014; Murray et al. 2010), in policy implementation (Mackenzie et al. 2018), and more recently in open research (Perreault and Dienlin 2024) and train-the-trainer evaluation (Krishnamoorthy et al. 2025), though, to our knowledge, not previously within “open research train-the-trainer evaluation”.

Relative to the train-the-trainer model, the NPT constructs are linked to the following implications:

- **Coherence** → trainers understood their role within the training cascade model;
- **Cognitive Participation** → they understood how to take on that role;
- **Collective Action** → local delivery was coordinated and took place;
- **Reflexive Monitoring** → trainers participated in assessing the programme's efficacy.

A more detailed operationalisation of the NPT constructs as used in this study is summarised in Table 1.

Table 1. NPT constructs as operationalised in this study.

NPT construct	Operationalisation in this study (the work it names)	Illustrative interview extract
Coherence (sense-making)	How trainers understood what the T3 programme required and how it differed from other training	“It wasn’t very clear to us how many sessions we needed to have attended, which ones were fundamental.” (FG2A.15)
Cognitive Participation (relational work)	Whether trainers could legitimately take on, own, and sustain the onward-delivery role	“That ownership felt really important... going on and sharing it and integrating it into my own practice.” (P1, FG1.19)
Collective Action (operational work)	The practical enactment of local delivery within institutional constraints	“I was just basically taking away the information I needed and just incorporating it into my bite sized sessions.” (P2, FG2B.24)
Reflexive Monitoring (appraisal work)	How trainers assessed effectiveness and whether evidence travelled back to the programme	“We do send them a similar survey... and we usually only get 2–3 people really responding to that.” (P2, FG2B.38)

A written conversation guide was developed using the NPT subconstructs as a framework and circulated to participants in advance of the interview (S4 Table). Researchers asked follow up questions where appropriate. Sessions were recorded and transcribed using Microsoft Teams and edited with reference to the recordings to form a precise record of what was said. The qualitative analysis operated on a corpus of 134 annotated transcript turns and made use of a deductive coding framework, with NPT subconstructs as codes (1.1–1.4, 2.1–2.4, 3.1–3.4, 4.1–4.4).

Each coded unit was a speaker turn, defined as one participant’s contribution before another speaker took the floor. Distinct portions of a lengthy speaker turn were sometimes mapped to more than one code. Coding was conducted separately by two researchers, before a third researcher reviewed the coding and offered an additional opinion on discrepancies. Adjudication was discursive, supported by light-weight statistics, which confirmed that as the emphasis of the interview discussions varied, as did the applied codes.

Participants and context

The UKRN T3 programme operates across 24 UK higher education institutions. Save for one institution, all reported at least one instance of local onward delivery of training, with over 2700

local trainees across all institutions. Semi-structured small group interviews were conducted with T3 participants across four sessions. A purposive sampling strategy was used to recruit participants: nine participants (n=9) were recruited via an email invitation sent to all members of the UKRN Training Community of Practice, an opt-in network of those who have attended a T3 course. The reachable population included approximately 200 members, from 23 of the 24 participating institutions.

While the sample size reflects a low response rate, rather than an overt saturation-based stopping rule (as had been planned in the preregistration), the coded transcripts were nevertheless sufficient to build a well-articulated understanding of how the Train-the-Trainer role was taken up across varied roles and contexts. The participants represented nine distinct institutions and held varied job roles including that of software engineer, librarian, researcher, and training professional. Career stages were varied, but most participants were early or mid-career. Analysis of transcripts proceeded via deductive NPT coding, with two coders and an adjudicator, as described above.

Table 2 summarises the four interview sessions, the number of participants in each, and the roles represented.

Table 2. Participants and roles by interview session (n = 9).

Session	Participants	Roles represented
FG1	2	early-career clinical researcher; train-the-trainer programme lead
FG2A	2	lecturer (physics); Open Research Coordinator/Administrator (ORCA)
FG2B	2	research software engineer; research-support librarian
FG3	3	scholarly-communications/research-support librarian; research integrity officer; Open Research Coordinator/Administrator (ORCA)
Total	9	research software engineers, librarians, researchers, and training/coordination professionals; mostly early or mid-career

Results: Normalisation work within the T3 cascade

Quotes are attributed to (anonymised) participants by focus-group identifier and turn number. Focus groups are labelled FG1, FG2A, FG2B, and FG3 (FG2A and FG2B are the two sessions of the second focus group). For example, the first quote is participant 2 in focus group 2B, turn 2 (“P2, FG2B.2”).

Coherence

Making sense of the T3 programme, the course requirements, prerequisites, and expectations of onward delivery, was an ongoing, evolving process. Broadly, participants understood that T3 was designed to build capacity for delivering open research training within their institutions: to upskill themselves and then reproduce that training locally (P2, FG2B.2; P2, FG1.1; P1, FG3.0).

A shared baseline coexisted with real ambiguity at the point of entry, however. Several participants were unclear which sessions were required versus optional (FG2A.15) or did not initially realise the courses carried onward-delivery and research commitments (FG2B.1). Expectations around designing, delivering, and evaluating their own training were varied, and participants felt these were often implicit rather than explicitly communicated.

Where expectations were made explicit, confidence in onward delivery rose. A template of “what was expected” was valued even when the content itself was familiar (FG3.4). Where they were not, participants were left to “put the pieces of the puzzle together” themselves (P2, FG2A.5). T3’s flexibility was thus an asset only once its core purpose and components were shared; without that grounding, trainers had to piece the programme together unaided.

Table 3. Coherence: illustrative extracts.

Source	Extract
P2, FG2B.2	“we would learn various aspects of open research and then just have to reproduce that in our own training sessions at our institution”
P2, FG1.1	“an opportunity to both ... upskill myself in open research practices, but then also ... bring that to colleagues ... It was only later ... I appreciated the community of practice and the wider network”
P1, FG3.0	“the programme is designed to help people become confident in delivering a training type session in relation to open research”
FG2A.15	“It wasn’t very clear to us how many sessions we needed to have attended, which ones were fundamental ... and which ones then were optional.”

Source	Extract
FG2B.1	“I didn’t realise when I first signed up ... these courses were part of [the UKRN Open Research Programme] research project as well ... I wasn’t really aware of the follow-up aspects”
FG3.4	“It was useful to have a template of what was expected ... the content, in and of itself, wasn’t necessarily new ... but it was useful to have it in a template.”
P2, FG2A.5	“it was up to you to try and put the pieces of the puzzle together and see how everything fits.”

Cognitive Participation

Engagement with T3 was shaped by individual motivation, the local institutional context, and the chance to take ownership of delivery. Some participants saw T3 as a way to enhance their own understanding of open research and improve research culture. For others, initial participation was driven by external expectations, with engagement strengthening only once they saw value in the discussions and potential impact (P1, FG2A.8). A framework and prompt to act could itself be the trigger to deliver at all (FG1.25).

Sustained involvement, however, was contingent on resources —above all time and support — and participants frequently stressed the importance of working with colleagues to embed and extend delivery (P2, FG2A.22; P2, FG2B.27).

Role legitimacy, as perceived both by participants and by others at their institutions, also shaped participation. “Impostor syndrome” was raised by some T3s who felt they had learned less than they had hoped from the courses. While many felt open research training aligned with their values and professional goals, it was often one responsibility among many rather than a core part of their role (P1, FG2B.19), and some in research-support roles felt the legitimacy of their offering was questioned (FG3.9).

Sustained engagement was most evident where participants developed a sense of ownership over the training and its application; access to materials, peer support, and institutional backing helped them integrate T3 into their own practice (P1, FG1.19).

Table 4. Cognitive Participation: illustrative extracts.

Source	Extract
P1, FG2A.8	“The first one was like... I need to tick the box... but then the discussion... I thought other people can benefit out of it.”

Source	Extract
FG1.25	"I wouldn't have delivered that training in [institution] if I hadn't had this framework, and this kind of prompt to be like, hey, here's some tools, go do your thing."
P2, FG2A.22	"to put everything together requires so much time and energy that we don't have."
P2, FG2B.27	"Maybe it's a case of linking up with other areas in my university and making sure we're all ... delivering the open research stuff in a more united way."
P1, FG2B.19	"It does fit into my role... it's just that it's a relatively small percentage of my role."
FG3.9	"The institution thinks of the library as 'books', not as research-supporting."
P1, FG1.19	"That ownership felt really important... going on and sharing it and integrating it into my own practice."

Collective Action

Participants described how they tried to enact their T3 role to fit into ongoing activities within their existing institutional structures and constraints. Successful delivery of training often occurred when open research training was incorporated into sessions that were already running, or where materials were adapted into shorter sessions.

This approach allowed participants to work within constraints on time and attendance, particularly given the difficulty of engaging researchers in longer sessions.

As a result, delivery was often simplified or shortened, for example through shorter online sessions or integration into seminar series.

This flexibility facilitated training delivery. Participants also emphasised the importance of working with colleagues to deliver and refine training over time. This included co-delivery, sharing practical approaches, and drawing on the wider UKRN Community of Practice.

However, not all participants felt they had the same opportunities for collaboration. Some participants described limited access to relevant peers, and being seen as the only person responsible for training delivery.

At an organisational level, delivery constraints were shaped by institutional structures, including how training sessions were promoted and resourced. Participants described challenges in coordinating across departments, attracting attendees, and fitting training into existing systems. In large institutions in particular, training provision may be fragmented across multiple groups.

Generally, enacting T3 training required participants to actively adapt delivery formats, as well as adapt delivery to fit their local context; however, success depended on various factors; in some cases, the train-the-trainer course itself was the limiting factor.

Successful implementation depended on participants' ability to integrate training into existing work, collaborate with others, and navigate institutional constraints. Despite this, some participants felt that participation in the train-the-trainer programme did not provide them with the skills or capacity to operationalise their own training.

In practice, this meant that engagement with the programme unevenly translated to delivery, and this correlated with differing confidence and perceived capacity among participants. This resulted in variable and locally contingent forms of delivery, rather than consistent onward delivery across institutions.

Table 5. Collective Action: adaptation routes, enabling conditions, and failure modes.

Each row pairs an adaptation route trainers used with the institutional condition that enabled it and the failure mode observed in its absence. Routes are derived implications from the interviews, not measured effects.

Adaptation route	Enabling condition	Failure mode when absent	Illustrative evidence
Fold OR training into sessions already running	An existing session or audience to attach to	Standalone sessions fail to recruit	"fallen into... incorporating it into things that I'm already doing" (P1, FG1.28); "hard to get researchers to give up like half a day" (P1, FG2B.31)
Shorten or move delivery online	Format flexibility; permission to adapt	Material too long/broad to land locally	"only short 30 minute sessions... we just present it" (P1, FG2B.22)
Co-deliver and draw on the Community of Practice	Access to relevant peers; an active CoP	Isolation; the trainer carries delivery alone	"worked... with colleagues... making those connections" (P1, FG1.3); "more or less a single person at my institution" (FG3.9)

Adaptation route	Enabling condition	Failure mode when absent	Illustrative evidence
Establish a clear locus of ownership for OR training across the institution	A unified structure with defined responsibility	Coordination/ownership deficit — surfacing as a single-person bottleneck in small institutions and as fragmentation across groups in large ones	small: “the responsibility of a single individual” (FG3.9); large: “fragmented across multiple groups” (FG2B.49); “no unified... structure, who’s in charge” (FG3.6)
Equip trainers to operationalise their own delivery	T3 course builds delivery capacity, not just awareness	Trainers value the course but feel unequipped to deliver	“didn’t come out of it feeling equipped enough to deliver” (FG2A.4); “didn’t feel well enough equipped to then go on and train” (P3, FG2A)

Across institutions of varying size, a common deficit in coordination led to uncertainty around ownership and responsibility: small institutions described training as the responsibility of a single individual (FG3.9), while large institutions described provision as fragmented across multiple groups (FG2B.49), with “no unified... structure, who’s in charge” (FG3.6). The illustrative extract for each adaptation route and its failure mode is given in the table above.

Reflexive Monitoring

Participants reflected positively on T3, citing increased confidence and knowledge, and engagement with open research as a broader movement. However, these appraisals rested largely on informal, localised evaluation, with limited evidence of longer-term or wider impact.

Formal and informal modes of assessment coexisted. Post-session surveys were an expected evaluation route, but completion was variable and the returns partial (P1, FG2B.36; P2, FG2B.38). In their absence, participants leaned on more immediate signals — engagement in the room, or follow-up contact afterwards (P1, FG2B.39; FG3.18). These were meaningful locally, but participants stressed how hard it was to tell whether training translated into sustained changes in practice, and that it was often “too early just to know” (P2, FG2B.35; P1, FG2A.16).

The programme’s structure also shaped what could be evaluated: even where individual sessions were valued, the absence of a clear overarching narrative made it difficult to judge relevance or to target delivery to a specific audience (P2, FG2A.27; P1, FG2A). What evaluation did occur was frequently collaborative and practice-based — team debriefs and iterative refinement — a learning-by-doing that served, for some, as the main mechanism of appraisal in the absence of formal metrics (P1, FG2B.42; P2, FG2B.44; FG3.3).

Overall, reflexive monitoring was largely localised and informal. While participants were able to iteratively adapt and refine their practice, opportunities for more structured and shared evaluation across the programme were limited, making it difficult to evidence impact beyond individual or institutional contexts.^[Note 2]

Table 6. Reflexive Monitoring: illustrative extracts.

Source	Extract
P1, FG2B.36	“in terms of knowing whether the training that we deliver is useful, we always do surveys... it can be hard to get people to fill in the post workshop surveys, but as long as we get like a few answers and nobody says this was terrible, I generally think it’s gone quite well”
P2, FG2B.38	“We do send them a similar survey... at the end of each session and we usually only get 2–3 people really responding to that”
P1, FG2B.39	“even if you then don’t get the feedback survey, you can kind of tell whether people are engaged”
FG3.18	“the other thing that tells me that the programme and the training is effective is the fact that we have more and more contacts, more and more people that follow up... weeks or months later”
P2, FG2B.35	“it’s really difficult to measure how... training you’re redelivering then is actually having an impact”
P1, FG2A.16	“That’s a hard thing to tell [whether training is influencing researcher behaviour]... it’s a bit too early just to know”
P2, FG2A.27	“Each and every session was very valuable... it just lacked this common thread”
P1, FG2A	“if the training was more structured... this part is for this area... that would help us to think... OK I want to deliver something for PhD students...”
P1, FG2B.42	“we tend to do like a debrief within the team... see what went well? What didn’t”
P2, FG2B.44	“we just discussed what went well... and what we can improve next time based on the feedback we got”
FG3.3	“we’ve learned by doing”

Summary of findings and future work

The findings presented above make it clear that the programme's challenge is not persuasion, insofar as participating T3s already valued open research, but rather, institutionalisation: the construction of conditions under which individual effort can persist, travel, and be reinforced. The NPT framework has helped to clarify the challenges faced by those doing the work to embed open research in institutional culture and practices (C. May and Finch 2009; C. R. May et al. 2018). In relation to Perreault and Dienlin's application of NPT to open research (Perreault and Dienlin 2024), the present study shifts the unit of analysis from individual researchers adopting practices to a programme attempting to reproduce those practices through a cascade. Across the four constructs, onward delivery depended less on the training content — which participants broadly valued — than on local institutional conditions. These included a shared understanding of the programme's purpose and what onward delivery required (Coherence); the time, role legitimacy, and sense of ownership needed to act on it (Cognitive Participation); structures for coordinating delivery and a clear locus of responsibility for it (Collective Action); and the means to evidence impact beyond the immediate session (Reflexive Monitoring). Where these conditions were present, individual effort persisted and travelled. Where they were absent, it stalled regardless of commitment — yielding variable, locally contingent delivery rather than consistent reproduction across institutions.

Future work. The trainee-facing (T1) phase has been planned, ethics-approved, and preregistered; results will appear in a companion paper. The central finding of the present phase — that effective onward delivery depends more on local institutional conditions than on the training itself — motivates a structural hypothesis: that the trainer and trainee levels are *near-decomposable* (Simon 1962). This is coupled only weakly at the point of delivery, with the forces driving normalisation largely internal to each level. The companion study tests this by seeking to disconfirm the argument, using a maximum-variation sample of trainees spanning supportive and unsupportive institutional contexts, and across stronger and weaker local delivery. For example, a trainee in a supportive institution whose uptake nonetheless tracked delivery quality — or uptake in an unsupportive institution driven by strong training alone — would refute the decomposition. Absence of such cases is consistent with the decomposition, though not proof of it.

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Declarations

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- Author contribution:
 - Joseph Corneli — Conceptualization, Methodology, Formal Analysis, Data Curation, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing.
 - Kate Goldie — Conceptualization, Methodology, Formal Analysis, Validation, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing.
 - Danny Smith — Project Administration, Methodology, Formal Analysis, Data Curation, Writing – review & editing.
 - Steve Boneham — Methodology, Writing – review & editing, Project Administration.
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 - Neil Jacobs — Supervision, Project Administration, Funding Acquisition, Writing – review & editing.
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Supporting information

S1 Text. COM-B self-report survey summary (immediate post-T3). Instrument, COM-B framing, data provenance, and a summary of item-level responses on a privacy-preserving synthetic dataset. Presents S1 Fig and S1–S2 Tables. (supplement-comb.md)

S1 Fig. COM-B and normalisation self-report item means (synthetic, N = 57). Mean agreement (1–7) per item with ± 1 SD, coloured by COM-B component versus institutional / normalisation context. (figS1-comb-item-means.png)

S1 Table. Canonical COM-B items, immediate post-T3 (synthetic, N = 57). (in S1 Text)

S2 Table. Institutional / normalisation items, lowest first (synthetic, N = 57). (in S1 Text)

S3 Table. COREQ 32-item checklist. Completed Consolidated Criteria for Reporting Qualitative Research checklist (Tong et al. 2007). (supplement-coreq.md)

S4 Table. Focus-group question guide. The NPT-framed conversation guide used by facilitators. (supplement-question-guide.md)

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Notes

1. COM-B (Michie et al., 2011) informed a short self-report survey administered immediately after T3 (summarised in S1 Text, with S1 Fig). Because the response rate was low and the responses are not releasable as open data, we treat the material as indicative only and report it on a privacy-preserving synthetic dataset. It corroborates the qualitative analysis: trainers rated their own capability and motivation above the scale midpoint, while the lowest-rated items concerned institutional conditions — leadership, resourcing, measurement, and sustainability — rather than individual capacity.
2. More intensive centralised approaches to participatory evaluation had been discussed; the specific proposal that research evaluation be a participatory open research project in its own right (Corneli 2023, <https://doi.org/10.57874/e1hk-b246>) was deemed too demanding for participants with mixed roles and scarce time.